

DEVELOPMENT LAWS OF LITERARY LANGUAGE AND UZBEK
LITERARY STANDARDS

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ANNOTATION

This article gives information about development laws of literary language and uzbek literary standards and their qualities and functions.

Key words: synharmonism, dialect, standard, development, history of language

Development is an objective, dialectical process, which occurs due to the changes that occur as a result of the transition from one quality to another quality. Every object and event in the world is in constant motion. Similarly, language is always changing. This is related to the life of the society to which the language is directly related, its constant movement and development. If the society stops this movement or if this connection is cut off, then the language will stop developing and disappear. : synharmonism, dialect, standard, development, history of language There are internal and external factors in language development. If the internal factors of language development are based on the specific development of levels in the language system, the external factors are reflected in linguistic, or rather extralinguistic phenomena such as language and society, interlinguistic relations and influence, speech process, assimilation, layers. Accordingly, linguistics is divided into 2: internal linguistics and external linguistics. While internal linguistics studies the internal structure and system of language, external linguistics studies the social significance and function of language, i.e. how a person living in society, the speaker uses language, and the impact of language on society, as well as on the same and different language families. researches the interaction of related languages, the changes that occur as a result of external influences on the language. Internal linguistic laws are reflected at the levels of the language system. Linguistic regularities appear in their own way. From this point of view, general and specific laws can be observed in language development. General laws mean linguistic events and processes typical of all languages. For example, the communicative and expressive functions of the language, the uneven development of language levels, that is, the rapid change of the lexical layer compared to other linguistic layers, constant movement, etc. Specific linguistic factors include specific rules of each

concrete language, for example, each language (even languages belonging to the same language family) has its own phonetic system, lexical level, grammatical structure, and stylistic styles. So, these two types of laws or factors require each other; generality includes features. Let's move on to the analysis of internal development features of linguistic levels. The phenomenon of linguistic development is mainly studied in three aspects: lexical, phonetic, grammatical. unevenly. The most rapidly developing, mobile part of the language is the vocabulary. A lexeme is a constantly changing, renewable layer. The material and spiritual life of people is undoubtedly reflected in the lexicon. This can be observed in the phenomenon of neologisms and archaisms that occur today. As science and technology, science and worldview grow, new words appear in our language: cosmonaut, nuclear, clip, pop, computer, Internet, e-mail, system, lexeme, etc. Also, words that do not participate in social and political life become obsolete in the language system and become archaisms or historicisms: bozchi, mirob, faytun, qazi, amir, saroybon, obkom, raykom, etc. In the recent past, the words "raycom", "tractor", "television", and "radio" were neologisms, new words. Nowadays, most of them have become a lexicon of everyday speech. In addition, there are many methods in the language system, such as integration, terminologicalization, and simplification, which serve to change the content of the dictionary. The use of words in a figurative sense is an important factor in the development of vocabulary. Examples are white gold, golden hands, wolf (in the negative sense of a person), fox, snake (in the sense of cunning), aunt, father, uncle (in the figurative sense of a stranger) belongs to this category. Internal laws of language development are more concretely reflected in phonetics. It is known that phonetics studies speech sounds and phonetic division of speech. In phonetics, there are many laws, such as assimilation, dissimilation, synharmonism, diphthongization, enclisis, proclisis qualitative development of this language, because quantitative changes between layers (math) in the language are generalized in grammar and serve as an internal factor for the development of grammatical categories and means of expressing grammatical meaning. The ratio of grammatical categories in languages is not the same, for example, the distinguishing feature of nouns in English and German is that in German (as well as in Russian) there is a root category: tad (day) - muj.r. wasser – (water) -serd.r.; yunge (language) gen.r. This phenomenon also occurred in Old English: doy (day) muj.r.; water (water) – average; tongue (language) – gen.r. Dialects are studied as dialectisms in language systems. Dialects are a territorial concept, a specific language of people living in a certain territory, different from the literary language. The branch of linguistics that studies dialects and dialects is called dialectology. It describes phonetic, morphological, syntactic and lexical features of

dialects and dialects. The role of dialects in the emergence and development of the national language, the dialects that form the basis of the national language are determined. Dialects, as well as their relationship with literary language and related languages are determined.

REFERENCES

1. Ниятова, М. (2022). Significant points on assessment procedure. *Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы*, 1(1), 587–589. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5345>
2. Abduganieva, M., & Niyatova, M. (2023). WHAT IS A CONTENT IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE?. *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences*, 2(11), 157–162. извлечено от <http://econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/6941>
3. Abduraxmanova, Z., & Mamurova, M. (2021). THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SPEECH DISFLUENCIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 43-45).
4. Ma'ripov J. K. A BRIEF INFORMATION ABOUT TENSES //O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O‘RTA. – С. 464.
5. Rahmatullayevna, A. D. (2022). KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETESIYANI SHAKLLANTIRUVCHI TARJIMA USULLARI.
6. Ахмедова С. Р. Таълим ва тарбия жараёнлари узвийлигининг самарадорлиги //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 369-373.